

**THE IMPORTANCE OF WORKING WITH THE
DICTIONARY IN SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN DEVERTED
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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the role of working with vocabulary in bringing speech of children with developmental delays to the level of their healthy peers. The study analyzed the formation of vocabulary in such children, the volume of active and passive vocabulary, methods of their expansion, and the mechanisms of speech therapy influence. Also, the teacher substantiated the need to control the vocabulary of children in accordance with age standards, the correctness of pronunciation, the development of intonation and phonemic perception. Through systematic work on vocabulary, children with developmental delays develop communication skills and reach the level of free speech like their healthy peers.

Today, world statistics show an increase in speech defects among children. Therefore, the prevention of speech disorders in children and adolescents, the organization of correctional and pedagogical work with them has become an urgent area of modern defectology and speech therapy. In the education system of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to working with children with developmental delays (with delayed mental development or impaired speech development).

Although the formation of speech in children with developmental delays depends on many factors, expanding their vocabulary, teaching them to correctly understand and use the semantic content of words is of central importance. Insufficient vocabulary development leads to difficulties in all aspects of a child's speech - phonetic-phonemic, lexical, grammatical, and communicative.

Children's vocabulary development: norms and deviations. The formation of vocabulary in normally developing children proceeds as follows: at the age of 3, the vocabulary usually consists of 1000-1200 words. At this age, the child can use most parts of speech, begins to form simple and complex interrogative sentences. The period from 1 to 3 years is a stage of intensive development of active speech. In the age range of 4-6 years, active vocabulary reaches 3000-4000 words.

Conversely, in children who do not speak or whose speech is sharply delayed, the active vocabulary may consist of 5-10, and in some cases, 20-30 word combinations. In such children, poor vocabulary is accompanied by late speech development, agrammatism, pronunciation errors, and low phonemic perception. The logopedic significance of working with a dictionary. Enriching vocabulary in working with children with developmental delays is one of the central directions of speech therapy impact. The tasks of the speech therapist are as follows: expanding passive vocabulary: the child should hear more words, try to understand them. Formation of active vocabulary: the child should be able to independently use words in communication. Developing a vocabulary of verbs (sitting, walking, coming, etc.) - this is very important in grammatical formation. Teaching the correct pronunciation of sounds: the differentiation of the sounds m, n, b, p,

g is of particular importance. Elimination of agrammatisms: correct use of singular-plural, possessive suffixes, cases. Working on intonation and rhythm: short poems, songs, rhythmic exercises help.

One of the most important principles in working with vocabulary is not to criticize a child for errors in their speech, but to gently correct and support them. Stress further slows down speech development.

Early stages of speech: from birth to school age. In the prelingual period, at the moment of birth, the child activates the vocal apparatus through screaming and crying. At 2 weeks, they start paying attention to adults' voices. At 1 month, it calms down to the melody of a lullaby - this indicates the formation of intonation perception. Humming begins at 2-3 months of age. At 5 months, the child hears sounds and begins to imitate articulatory movements. Between 6-9 months, syllable repetition (na-na-na; da-da-da) is observed.

In the period of the first words (1-3 years), at 1 year and 6 months, the child usually has 10-15 words. By the end of 2 years, the vocabulary reaches 250-300 words. From the age of 2, two-word sentences appear: "give me the flower," "see." During this period, grammatical forms are only beginning to form.

In the preschool period (3-6 years), easily pronounced consonants: p, b, m, f, v are mastered first. Difficult sounds: s, z, sh, j, ch, r, l, k, g are pronounced distorted in many children. At 4-6 years of age, grammatical structure develops rapidly: complex sentences and compound sentences appear. Phonemic perception is strengthened.

In school age (7-17 years), the volume of vocabulary expands day by day. Abstract concepts are easily assimilated. Along with the development of written speech, grammatical norms are strengthened.

Practical methods used in vocabulary development include:

1. Sound imitation exercises (machine - "brr," bird - "chiq-chiq").
2. Introduction to objects (color, size, shape, properties).
3. Memorizing and singing rhythmic poems strengthens articulation and intonation.
4. Game technologies: "What has changed?" "Who does what?" "Find and say."
5. Create a short story: begin by saying 2-3 sentences based on the picture.
6. Teaching grammatical forms: singular-plural, possessive, verb tenses.

These methods, along with enriching vocabulary, also form communication skills. The speech development of children with developmental delays largely depends on their vocabulary. Phased, systematic, and scientifically based work on the dictionary:

- the emergence and consolidation of speech,
- development of phonemic perception,
- formation of grammatical structures,
- ensures the expansion of social communication skills.

Vocabulary exercises conducted jointly by a speech therapist, teacher, and parent bring the child's speech closer to the level of healthy peers and create a solid foundation for their intellectual development.

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